

BIO-UPTAKE: BIOcomposites in smart plastic transformation processes to pave the way for the large-scale UPTAKE of sustainable bio-based products

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The context

In 2020, the European Green Deal was adopted with the aim of transforming EU's strategies for achieving climate neutrality by 2050 and a prosperous and fair society. This involves new paradigms and policies related with sustainable growth, **circularity and bio-economy**, among others.

Replace fossil-based materials by bio-based, recyclable, biodegradable.

BIO-UPTAKE

- ❖ Increase the uptake of bioplastic composites by 39%.
- ❖ Develop flexible manufacturing processes to produce biobased end-products for the construction, medical and packaging sectors.

Team: 14 partners

6 industries:

SIMCON

4 RTOs:

2 Academia:

2 Associations:

Objectives

- SO1: develop 3 **disruptive innovative manufacturing processes** for bio-based products with a better performance than fossil-based alternatives.
- SO2: adapt and upgrade 6 **conformal manufacturing technologies**.
- SO3: implement a **smart digital end-to-end platform** for manufacturing biobased materials.
- SO4: develop and validate 4 **new biobased intermediate** formats or **semi-finished products**.
- SO5: demonstrate Biouptake's **solution in 3 manufacturing value chains** (construction, medical and packaging).
- SO6: develop 3 **end-products** (bathroom ceiling cabinet, feet orthosis and garbage container lid) made of **more than 75% biobased materials**.
- SO7: demonstrate **product circularity** (reusability, remanufacturability and/or recyclability).
- SO8: **create 2 training programmes** for upskilling professionals in circular economy and smart & green manufacturing practices.
- SO9: **contribute to standardization**, applied to the 3 manufacturing value chains driving biomaterials uptake.

WP7 – Project management

WP6 – Exploitation, dissemination and communication

WP1 – Manufacturing plan, sustainability assessment and good practices distillation

WP5 – Demonstrate innovative biobased material production and biobased products

WP2

Optimization and manufacturing of intermediate biocomposite formats

WP3

Optimization of the manufacturing processes for final biocomposite products

WP4

Digital systems and interoperability

Task 3.6–E&H safety characterisation

Standard experiments with bio-based materials and intermediate products: environmental safety

Standard experiments with bio-based materials and intermediate products: human safety

Characterization of pathogens in foot orthosis & bath ceiling.

Weathering influence on garbage lid environmental safety.

Safer materials and products for Environmental and Human Health

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